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SOCIAL SECURITY WELFARE, DONATION AS INSTRUMENTS OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY OVER PERFORMANCE OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN NIGERIA

¹Ugwuanyi James Uchenna, ²Prof. Nebo Gerald Nwora and ³Okafor Ozoemena Christian (Ph.D.)

¹Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, (Esut)

²Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (Esut)

³Department of Marketing, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (Esut)

E-mail: ugwuanyijames1967@gmail.com, gerald.nebo.@esut.edu.ng, peter.ozoemena@yahoo.com

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Abstract: The aim of this study was to investigate the influence social security welfare, donation as instrument of corporate social responsibility over financial performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. Specific objectives include to: determine the individual influence of social security welfare and donations on profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. Ex post facto research design was adopted for the study. Auto-distributed lag model (ARDL) regression technique was used in testing hypotheses. After data analysis, findings revealed that social security welfare had a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria ($F=2.857131$, $pv=0.0000<0.05$) and donation exert a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria ($F=2.705764$, $pv=0.0000<0.05$). It was recommended that commercial banks should continue to engage in payments of social security welfare packages (such as hospital bills and pension for retirees) to their staff as this will go a long way in maintaining mutual relationship between the staff and the bank. Social security welfare packages motivate bank employees for higher performance which will invariably contribute to commercial banks' profitability and commercial banks should continue to make donation to the less-privileged such as the motherless baby homes, the school of social welfare, victims of flood, fire, tornado and war disasters. Others are donations for community social infrastructures, (e.g schools, hospitals, markets, power and pipe borne waster) and development projects (e.g skill acquisitions and provision of capital to small scale investors).

Keywords: Social security welfare, donations, corporate social responsibility, financial performance, commercial banks

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INTRODUCTION

These CSR activities became an aspect of donations and charitable gifts to individuals, groups, communities, charity homes, establishments, and provision of public goods and services to the general public. CSR is engaged to address economic and societal interests during the course of the bank's business. In spite of this reasoning, shareholders argue that the business of business is to increase profit for the owners and it is important to get the business of business right first. They express fear over the danger of allowing the managers to play around with shareholders' funds in the name of CSR because of divergence of interest of the principal and agent as predicted by the agency theory (Lasukova, 2015). The presence of organizations in the society, however, does not come without certain challenges, as their day-to-day activities are expected to be conducted ethically and legally while also committing themselves to the realization of their stakeholders' expectations. This brings about the concept of corporate social responsibility which is regarded as crucial to the achievement of these expectations. CSR means that companies must not only fulfill shareholders' needs but also take into consideration other stakeholders' demands (Tuhin, 2014).

Corporate Social Responsibilities (CSR) has been a highly contemporary and contextual issue to all stakeholders, including the government, the corporate organization itself, and the general public. The public contended that the payment of taxes and the fulfillment of other civic rights are enough grounds to have the liberty to take back from the society in terms of CSR undertaken by other stakeholders. Some ten years ago, what characterized the Nigerian society was flagrant pollution of the air, of water and of the environment. Most corporate organizations are concerned about what they can take out of the society, and de-emphasized the need to give back to the society (their host communities). However, the general belief is that both business and society gain when firms actively strive to be socially responsible; that is, business organizations gain in terms of enhanced reputation, while society gains from the social projects executed by business organizations. In modern times, however, having seen the benefits and favourable pay-back of their investment in CSR, corporations are now seriously involved in this project, which had impacted in the society wonderfully and profitably (Adeyanju, 2012)

Organizations, including banks in Nigeria, are increasingly beginning to understand the importance of ensuring and creating value in society, which is expected to have a positive effect on the organization. The past few years have, however, left banks in Nigeria with no choice but to find creative ways of strengthening their corporate brands and appeal to the good conscience of stakeholders. For the forward looking ones who currently report their CSR activities, on their websites and /or annual financial report, corporate social investment has proved effective in improving their public perception and financial performance (Lawal & Brimah, 2012). Giving part of their profit to good course may not make sense on the face of it but the returns in terms of brand appeal can hardly be underestimated. Zenith Bank Plc has, for instance, set aside one percent (1%) of its Profit after Tax (PAT) for CSR activities. Committing a portion of PAT to CSR is to avoid suspicion of tax evasion. Likewise, First Bank of Nigeria Plc, GTBank Plc, Access Bank Plc, among a few others, quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), have been visible in the past doling out substantial amounts of money to different segments of society while reporting tax payments (Ameashi, Adi, Obeche & Amao, 2016).

A total of N1.869 billion was reported to have been spent by eight Nigerian banks in 2012 on various community-related projects under the rubric of corporate social responsibility to identify with the society in

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which they operate (Obi, 2018). The figure is about 55 percent of the total CSR expenditure of N3.4billion by the banking industry which is in contrast with N1.7billion, with the hope that the figures will increase in the future due to increased knowledge of the concept of CSR (Ameashi, *et al*, 2016). Among the eight banks, tier one banks (Zenith Bank Plc, UBA Plc, GTBank Plc, FBN Plc, and Access Bank Plc), which are ranked based on their huge market share, capital base, among other indices, dominated the list, with Zenith bank Plc topping the CSR expenditure list with N585million, followed by GTBank Plc which spent N364.8m. In 2011, the oil and gas sector spent N9.5billion on CSR, followed by telecoms with N6.4billion, and the banking industry came third (Obi, 2018).

The introduction of corporate social responsibility in 1960 has been considered as major step forward within the Nigeria banking industry. Though, much more are required to create an enabling environment for business practices to thrive and produce results, the banks that are truly committed to CSR will seek to create the change they desire, and not play victims of weak institutional context. The South East banking industry has been a mandatory task that requires banks to formulate strategic approach that balances both the environmental and social risks identified with business opportunities to be exploited for good firm financial performances.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria banks as the second most profitable in Africa based on the 2023 rising profit performance, yet many Nigeria deposit money banks have experienced poor performance in terms of illiquidity, insolvency, and undercapitalization resulting from unsustainable attribute of corporate social responsibility to enable them attract more customers, spread banking service to rural areas and thus South East banking industry have challenges with sustainable economic, legal, ethical, philanthropic and environmental marketing (Anaeto, 2015).

Despite the increasing rate of expansion of the banks and their businesses in Nigeria, there is hardly a commensurate evidence of recorded CSR expenditure undertaken by the banks to assist their host communities in areas of their socioeconomic needs and sustainable development. This corporate gesture of giving back to, and appreciation for their host communities should be acknowledged by banks, especially in investing in socio-economic and environmental development of these communities since they enjoy an interdependent relationship with them, yet little is being done to reverse the trend (Adeyanju, 2012). Based on this assertion, this study is to examine the influence of social security welfare, donation as instruments of corporate social responsibility on performance of commercial banks in Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the influence of social security welfare, donation as instrument of corporate social responsibility on performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. Specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the influence of social security welfare packages on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the influence of donation on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Social Corporate Responsibility

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Steiner (2017) defined Corporate Social Responsibilities (CSR) as “the intelligent and objective concern for the welfare of the society that retains the individual and corporate behaviour from ultimately destructive activities, no matter how immediately profitable and leads to the directions of positive construction of human betterment”. As an improvement on the above definitions, Koontz and O’Donnell (2018) defined social responsibility as the personal obligation of everyone, as he acts in his own interests, but he must always have due regard that his freedom does not restrict others from doing the same thing. He further noted that a socially responsible individual or organization will obey the laws of the land.

Corporate Social Responsibility in Nigerian Commercial Banks

Elkington (2018) emphasized that firms should not only focus on enhancing its value through maximizing profit and outcome, but also concentrate on environmental and social issues equally. The concept of CSR is generally accepted as tool for ensuring sustainability, while the term “sustainability” having emerged from the environmental perspective refers to the management of physical and non-physical resources, so that they are conserved for the future. The notion of sustainability is very specific. It means the long-term maintenance of balance. As elaborated by theorists including John Elkington, this balance is achieved economically, socially, and environmentally. However, the next section discusses the economic and social sustainability which are relevant to the current study

Social Security Welfare Packages

Social Security welfare refers as administrative strategy that protects workers for lifetime benefit. Social security welfare also deals with by providing replacement income for workers in times of death, disability, sickness, maternity and old age (Ferguson, 2019).

Donations

Donations can be defined as “the act of an enterprise donating free resources, cash and other intangible assets to a third party for free” (Financial Accounting Standards Board, 1993). first. In 1999, China passed the law to define donations as “the act of donating their own assets by individuals, organizations or enterprises to the society”. In 2016, defined donation is as “an activity in which natural persons, legal persons and other organizations donate property voluntarily and freely for charitable purposes” in the Charity Law.

Financial Performance of Commercial Banks

Nwachukwu (2000) listed some of the objectives and goals of organizations to include increase in profitability, growth, productivity, market share, sales volume, customer loyalty and competitiveness. If organizations must achieve these objectives, the need for performance monitoring and management becomes not only necessary, but imperative. The five adopted measures are profitability, sales volume, customer loyalty; market share and productivity have been briefly reviewed below;

Profitability as a Measure of Commercial Banks Performance

Profitability is the ability of a business to earn a profit. A profit is what is left of the revenue a business generates after it pays all expenses directly related to the generation of the revenue, such as producing a product, and other expenses related to the conduct of the business' activities (Grimsley, 2015).

CSR and Performance of Commercial Banks

Chih *et al.* (2010) examined a total of 520 financial firms in 34 countries over 2003-2005, and conclude categorically that CSR and financial performance are not related. The emphasis of this evidence was shifted by

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contradictory evidence presented by the study of Wu and Shen (2013). They analyzed 162 banks through 22 countries and over a 7 years (i.e. 2003- 2009), and revealed that CSR is positively associated with financial performance in terms of return on assets, return on equity, net interest income, and non-interest income. The differences in the results could be traced to possible issues relating to measurement, differences in sample size as well as study periods.

2.2.6 Conceptual Framework

The model further explains that relationship exist between social welfare package, donations, as instrument of corporate social responsibility over performance of commercial banks in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1: Model of Corporate Social Responsibility and Commercial Banks

Legitimacy theory was propounded by Suchman in (1995), Schman defines legitimacy as ‘a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs and definitions’(Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). Thus legitimacy might be seen as a key reason for undertaking corporate social behaviour and also then using that activity as a form of publicity or influence (Clarke, 1998). A converse view to this, i.e. not that business uses its power to legitimate its activity but, rather that society grants power to business which it expects it to use responsibly is set out by Davis (Wood, 1991): ‘Society grants legitimacy and power to business. In the long run, those who do not use power in a manner which society considers responsible will tend to lose it’. In effect, this is a re-statement of the concept of a social contract between the firm and society.

The study may begin, therefore, to examine the practice of CSR within business as potentially motivated by some form of principle as described in social contracts theory, analysed in the particular by some form of stakeholder analysis in order to provide enhanced reputation or legitimacy to the firm. This is, of course, not the only way to review the practice of CSR, however the separation into principles, practices and outcomes is a way to assess performance in the area.

Empirical Review

Sudan, Sunita and Yuantao (2023) examined social security, psychological threat, and corporate performance: An analysis of financial performance after enactment of a social security scheme in Nepal. The findings of the analysis revealed an adverse impact on corporate performance in the banking sector compared to the non-banking sector. The study also showed that the banking sector's psychological fear was greater than that of the non-banking sector after the implementation of the policy.

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Eke, Sotom and Odukwu (2023) examined employee welfare and financial performance of listed Nigerian manufacturing firms. This study investigated the relationship between employee welfare and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between employee welfare (ER and ET) and financial performance in terms of ROA of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Also, it was revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between employee welfare (ER and ET) and financial performance in terms of ROE of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Okike, Ekoja and Nyahas (2023) examined impact of philanthropic corporate social responsibility on firm value of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This study examines the impact of Philanthropic Social Responsibility on firm value of listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. Findings from the analysis revealed that philanthropic Social Responsibility has significant positive relationship with the firm value of deposit money banks (DMB's) in Nigeria.

Fan (2021) examined an empirical analysis of the relationship between charitable donation and enterprise performance based on the data of listed companies in China. Through charity Donations and other means to promote their own sustainable development and improve their own image, to achieve win-win results. Starting with charitable donations, this article analyzes the domestic and foreign literature and the present status of charitable donations in our country.

Oluwakemi, *et al* (2021) examined the effect of philanthropic responsibility on competitiveness of private universities in Nigeria. This paper examined the effect of philanthropic responsibility on competitiveness of private universities in Nigeria. The sample size was made up of 410 staff of selected universities which were selected based on stratified, random and convenient sampling techniques. The findings showed that philanthropic responsibility has a significant effect on competitiveness of private universities in Nigeria.

Kike, Ekoja and Nyahas (2023) investigated impact of philanthropic corporate social responsibility on firm value of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This study examines the impact of philanthropic social responsibility on firm value of listed Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study was motivated by conflicting findings by researchers on the relationship between Philanthropic Social Responsibility and firm value. Findings from the analysis revealed that philanthropic Social Responsibility has significant positive relationship with the firm value of deposit money banks (DMB's) in Nigeria.

Gap in Empirical Review

The few studies done were carried outside and did not focus on the social welfare package, donations as instrument of corporate social responsibility on performance of commercial banks in Nigeria especially on the dividend payments, tax payments against profitability in Nigeria. Therefore, the study was aimed at filling this research gap by examining the influence of corporate social responsibility of marketing and performance of commercial banks in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted *ex-post* facto design for this study. The choice of the *ex-post* facto design were because the research relied on already recorded data, and researchers do not have control over the relevant dependent and independent variables they are studying with a view to manipulating them (Onwumere, 2009). This study made use of secondary data of time series covering a period of 10 years i.e. 2014 – 2023, which were obtained

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from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), stock exchange group, and world development indicators statistical bulletin.

3Model Specification

The aim of this study was to examine the influence of social welfare package, donations as instrument of corporate social responsibility on performance of commercial banks in Nigeria. The study adopted model of Echekeba and Egbunike (2019). The model is specified in functional form and modified as follows:

$$PFY = f(SSW, DON) \text{ ----- (i)}$$

Transforming the data into a log form, the econometric model becomes;

$$LPFY_t = \alpha + \beta_1 LSSW_{t-1} + \beta_2 DON_{t-1} + \epsilon_{t-1} \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

Where;

LPFY = Profit for the Year (a proxy for Performance of Commercial Banks)

LSSW = Social Security Welfare

LDON = Donations

μ = Error Term

α = Constant

β = Regression coefficient

t = Time at Present

t-i = Time at lag i, i-1,2,

The apriori expectation (i,e, $\beta_1 \geq 0$)

Hypothesis One Model:

Social security welfare do not have significant positive influence on profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria.

$$LPFY_t = f(SSW_t) \text{ ----- (3.1)}$$

$$LPFY_{t-1} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SSW_{t-1} + \epsilon_{t-1} \text{ .. (3.2)}$$

Where,

LPFY_t =Profit for the Year

SSW_t = Social Security Welfare

β_0 =Constant

β_1 , =Proxies of the coefficient of the parameter estimates

ϵ =Error term

t =Time period

log =Log of the variables

A prior expectations: $\beta_1 > 0$

Hypothesis Two Model:

Donations do not have significant positive influence on profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria.

$$LPFY_{t-1} = f(DON_t) \text{ ----- (3.3)}$$

$$LPFY_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DON_{t-1} + \epsilon_{t-1} \text{ .. (3.4)}$$

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Where,

LPFY_{t-1} =Profit for the Year

LDON_t = Donations

β₀ =Constant

β₁, =Proxies of the coefficient of the parameter estimates

ε =Error term

t =Time period

log =Log of the variables

A priori expectations: β₁ > 0

Methods of Data Analyses

Time series data covering a period of 10 years was estimated using descriptive statistics, correlation test and unit root test. The study used Auto-distributed lag model (ARDL) regression analysis method to test hypothesis. However, Unit root test were carried out for each of the variables so as to ascertain the time series properties of the data set and obtain the stationary status. Unit root test or stationary test is a preliminary test done to prevent running a spurious regression.

The following regression model was adopted.

$$Y = B_0 + B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + B_3X_3 + B_4X_4 + e$$

Where; Y = Profit for the Year

X₃ = Social Security Welfare

X₄ = Donations

e is the error of prediction

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

This section describes the data used for the analysis under statistical tool such as mean, maximum, minimum and standard deviation. The behaviour and movement of the data are observed under these statistical tools and their associated variance. The result of the descriptive statistics is presented in Table 4.1

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

	LOGDON	LOGSSW	LOGPFY
Mean	14.38304	14.47519	13.68220
Median	13.17441	14.03754	12.17020
Maximum	22.91758	19.44373	19.16471
Minimum	7.126087	10.66872	7.463937
Std. Dev.	4.396752	2.139195	3.452811
Skewness	0.270031	0.711100	0.435171
Kurtosis	2.183109	2.896686	1.788484
Jarque-Bera	1.877998	4.151376	4.635974
Probability	0.391019	0.125470	0.098472
Obs	50	50	50

Source: Extracted from E-view 10 Package see appendix 1

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Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables and all the mean value of all the variables. Table 4.2.1 contains the description of the variables using normality test which comprises of Skewness, Kurtosis and Jarque – Bera Statistics. The table shows that the profit for the year, donations, social security welfare, are positively skewed relative not normally distributed.

Unit Root Test

In order to address the problem, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test was employed on the chosen data set to ascertain the stationarity of the data as follows:

Table 3 Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF	cv@5%	Probability	Inference
LOGGON	-5.657	-2.943	0.0000	1(1)
LOGSSW	-4.199	-2.93	0.0021	1(1)
LOGPFY	-6.871	-2.923	0.0000	1(1)

Source: extracted from E- View 10 package

The a priori expectation when using the ADF test is that a variable is stationary when the value of the ADF test statistic is more negative than the critical value at 5%. Table 4.2.4 shows that the profit for the year, donations, social security welfare are stationary at first difference. Based on this evidence, Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) will emerge as a best tool for testing hypotheses rather than Ordinary least Square since there was consistency of 1(1) in all the variables.

Test of Hypothesis One

Restatement of hypothesis in null and alternate form thus:

H_{a1}: Social security welfare packages do not have significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Social security welfare packages have significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LOGPFY(-1)	0.852722	0.091023	9.368182	0.0000
LOGSSW	0.471167	0.164909	2.857131	0.0066
LOGSSW(-1)	-0.363942	0.171573	-2.121204	0.0397
C	0.530606	1.836179	0.288973	0.7740
R-squared	0.786189	Mean dependent var		13.74261
Adjusted R-squared	0.771272	S.D. dependent var		3.539292
S.E. of regression	1.692685	Akaike info criterion		3.971774
Sum squared resid	123.2028	Schwarz criterion		4.129234
Log likelihood	-89.33670	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.031027
F-statistic	52.70407	Durbin-Watson stat		1.966771
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

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Table 4.3.3 above shows that the R^2 which measures goodness of fit is 0.786189, that is about 78%. This indicates that 78% change in the dependent variable being profit for the year is explained by the independent variables and the higher the R^2 the better fit the independent variables. The F – statistics which measure the significance of the regression model is 52.70407 while its probability value is 0.000000. This shows that the model is significant as the F –statistics is less than the probability value of 0.05. The Durbin – Watson stat (1.9) is approximately equal to two (2) indicating the absence of autocorrelation.

Decision: Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the t-statistics is 2.857131 and the probability value is < 0.05. Table 4.3.3 shows the t-statistics as 2.857131 while the probability is 0.0000>0.05. We reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and conclude that social security welfare exert a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Restatement of hypothesis in null and alternate form thus:

H_{a2} : Donations do not have significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.

H_{a2} : Donations do not have significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial Banks in Nigeria.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
LOGPFY(-1)	0.847905	0.085161	9.956432	0.0000
LOGDON	0.236520	0.087413	2.705764	0.0099
LOGDON(-1)	-0.184082	0.090498	-2.034113	0.0484
C	1.397536	1.128935	1.237925	0.2228
R-squared	0.771936	Mean dependent var		13.61819
Adjusted R-squared	0.755248	S.D. dependent var		3.307164
S.E. of regression	1.636134	Akaike info criterion		3.907237
Sum squared resid	109.7543	Schwarz criterion		4.067829
Log likelihood	-83.91282	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.967104
F-statistic	46.25794	Durbin-Watson stat		1.747713
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Table 4.3.4 above shows that the R^2 which measures goodness of fit is 0.77193, that is about 78%. This indicates that 78% change in the dependent variable being profit for the year is explained by the independent variables and the higher the R^2 the better fit the independent variables. The F – statistics which measure the significance of the regression model is 46.25794 while its probability value is 0.000000. This shows that the model is significant as the F –statistics is less than the probability value of 0.05. The Durbin – Watson stat (1.7) is approximately equal to two (2) indicating the absence of autocorrelation.

Decision: Given the decision criteria to reject H_0 if the t-statistics is 2.705764 and the probability value is < 0.05. Table 4.3.4 shows the t-statistics as 2.705764 while the probability is 0.0000>0.05. We reject the null

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hypothesis (H₀) and conclude that donations exert a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Objective One: Examine the Influence of Social Security welfare on Profitability of Selected Commercial Banks in Nigeria.

The result of hypothesis three shows that social security welfare exert a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria. In similar study of Sudan, Sunita and Yuantao (2023) who examined social security, psychological threat, and corporate performance. The study also showed that the banking sector's psychological fear was greater than that of the non-banking sector after the implementation of the policy.

Objective Two: Ascertain the Influence of Donation on Profitability of Selected Commercial Banks in Nigeria.

The result of hypothesis four shows that donations exert a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria. This is in agreement with study of Fan (2021) who examined an empirical analysis of the relationship between charitable donation and enterprise performance - based on the data of listed companies in China. Through charity Donations and other means to promote their own sustainable development and improve their own image, to achieve win-win results.

Summary of Findings

iii. Social security welfare had a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria ($F=2.857131$, $pv=0.0000<0.05$).

iv. Donation exert a significant positive influence on profitability of selected commercial banks in Nigeria ($F=2.705764$, $pv=0.0000<0.05$).

Conclusion

Based on findings, we conclude that social welfare package, donations remains instrument of corporate social responsibility against performance of commercial banks in Nigeria, The researcher further concluded that social security welfare and donation had a significant positive influence on profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following were recommended;

- 1) Commercial banks should continue to engage in payments of social security welfare packages (such as hospital bills and pension for retirees) to their staff as this will go a long way in maintaining mutual relationship between the staff and the bank. Social security welfare packages motivate bank employees for higher performance which will invariably contribute to commercial banks' profitability.
- 2) Commercial banks should continue to make donation to the less-privileged such as the motherless baby homes, the school of social welfare, victims of flood, fire, tornado and war disasters. Others are donations for community social infrastructures, (e.g schools, hospitals, markets, power and pipe borne waster) and development projects (e.g skill acquisitions and provision of capital to small scale investors). These philanthropic responsibility will invariably improve the profit of the bank.

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